

GENRE CHARACTERISTICS OF POPULAR SCIENTIFIC TEXTS AND ARTICLES TAUGHT IN PRIMARY CLASS TEXTBOOKS

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Abstract. *Explain in the article that both theoretical information and scientific observations are expressed in genre expressions using popular science texts and articles, which, in essence, serve to teach students in primary school textbooks.*

Keywords: *primary education, popular science texts and articles, patriotism, humanistic ideas, observation, reflection, journalism, independence, children's literature.*

For many years, primary education has been considered as an education focused mainly on providing students with elementary information about reading, writing, counting, etc., and realizing their imaginations about the world around them. In the years of independence, this stage of education set the task of comprehensive development of the student's personality. Primary education is the most important tool in the development of a child's mind. First of all, a student of junior school age should develop the desire and ability to learn. For this, the teacher is required to provide new information to the student, taking into account his interests and aspirations. The development path of Uzbekistan depended not only on socio-economic and political reforms, but also on raising the morale of the society. Accordingly, our head of state emphasized the need to pay attention to the priority of education in the formation of spirituality and to create conditions for improving the quality of education in Uzbekistan.

Already, from the first steps on the path to independence of our country, great importance has been attached to the goal of restoring and further improving our great spirituality, strengthening its national soil, bringing it to the level of world standards and skills based on the requirements of the times.

It forms the basis of work in the field of education, such as encouraging the young generation to study the national and universal, rich spiritual heritage of our people, and guiding them to demonstrate their abilities based on inculcating the ideas of hard work, patriotism, and humanity. is enough. After all, in a democratic society, children, in general, every person is brought up as a free thinker. If the child does not learn to think freely, it is inevitable that the effectiveness of the given education will be low. Of course, knowledge is needed. But knowledge is on its way. Independent thinking is also a great asset. In other words, instilling the essence of independent thinking into students in primary grades is the main characteristic of the new generation of school textbooks of the independence period. In this sense, reading and mother tongue are among the main subjects of general primary education. In this case, the student must know the reading lesson in order to express his thoughts, and his mother tongue in order to express it in writing. Reading and native language lessons are important in the growth of the student's level of thinking, in the formation of knowledge and skills, in the formation of scientific concepts and speech skills. The task of the mother tongue in primary education is to form the child's speech skills based on the norm. For this, it is necessary to improve the child's ability to express his thoughts, to increase his

vocabulary, to connect words together, to teach him to make sentences, and at the same time, to write his thoughts correctly in writing. will consist of teaching. Primary school textbooks serve the education of the student with attention to their essence. In particular, popular scientific texts and articles convey theoretical information, scientific observations, and arouse artistic and aesthetic pleasure in the reader. The thought in such texts affects the child quickly; important events, vital facts, opinions about mature historical figures, narrations and wisdom are the basis for forming the thinking of the young generation. For this reason, Central Asian thinkers Farabi and Abu Ali Ibn Sina paid attention to the importance of factors affecting human education. Farabi emphasized the importance of education in human development: "A person has two opportunities to become a good person - education and upbringing. Theoretical maturity is achieved through education, and education is the way to create moral value and practical activity in communication with people..." - he says. In general, all the great pedagogues of the world expressed their views about the forms and forms of education in different periods. Some ideas of the great Czech pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius (1592-1670) about the school system and education of children are important for our pedagogy today. The scientist identified four types of schools, such as, "Mother's school is in every family; mother tongue folk school in every community, every village and every inhabited place; gymnasium should be in every city, and academy should be in every state or larger region," he says. Comenius compared the four types of schools to the four seasons of the year. "Mother's School" reminds of a wonderful spring covered with buds and flowers of fragrant plants. "Mother Tongue" school is like a summer where some tomorrow's fruits are ripe and ripe. The gymnasium reminds us of the summer season when we collect the rich harvest from the fields, orchards and poplars and store it in the treasury of the mind. Finally, it is the winter in which the Academy distributes the harvested harvest, intending to spend it for a lifetime [2, 31-6.]. In particular, Comenius believes that children should know about the political and economic situation in the educational system at home and in the city to the extent necessary to understand the events that happen before their eyes every day. It indicates that scientific and popular articles and texts in the textbook are in harmony with their purpose. Or, to know the basics of cosmography, that the sky is round, that the earth is spherical, that the earth is surrounded by the ocean, that the seas and rivers are curved, that the larger continents, the main countries located in Europe, students, especially o It is necessary for them to learn and study the cities, mountains, rivers and other interesting things in their homeland. It is obvious that this is expressed in scientific texts and today it is adapted to a popular form in textbooks in addition to individual subjects.

When the great pedagogue talks about the European continent, it is understood that every student should know the territory of his Motherland well. Therefore, it is traditional that scientific and popular texts about Uzbekistan and its neighboring regions, or its regions, are given in primary school textbooks and play an important role in the education system. All things should be suitable for children's age. It should be taken into account that the child's nature is prone to cheerfulness, humor, hilarity, and does not like seriousness and ruthlessness. After all, it is necessary to explain the useful things in an interesting way so that he learns the serious things that will be needed someday in life, and learns them easily and with pleasure, and in this way, it is necessary to direct the child's mind in the direction we want. One of the great discoveries of Johann Heinrich Pestolozzi was the establishment of the first public schools in Switzerland. According to him, the purpose of the public school is: It was not to give children certain knowledge that they would later forget, but the school was to naturally create in them a conscious look at the nature and social

relations around them, and to raise them to be able to live and work independently. Such relations are emphasized in terms of recognition in the educational system. That is, it is understood that it has always been important to form a social worldview and independent observation skills for children from a young age. Moreover, the uniqueness of reading books of the period of independence attracts attention with the priority of such a spirit, more precisely, with the increasing weight of scientific and popular texts and articles.

Tolstoy gives instructions about what elementary education books should be like in describing his ideas about didactics. The materials included in the book should be interesting for children and should be easy for them to understand, written in simple language, not verbose. Based on his didactic views and requirements for textbooks, Tolstoy created the "Reading Book" published in 1872. Later, this book was revised twice and published in 1875 under the name "New reading book". High artistry, expressiveness, brevity and simplicity, comprehensibility and attractiveness of the material for children were important features of Tolstoy's books. It can be said that such requirements determine the content goal of reading books of the independence period. Examples of folklore in textbooks, examples of literary and artistic creativity, and popular scientific texts and articles is the formation of scientific outlook, thinking and potential. There are various factors that make the student mature as a person. Each educational subject, in accordance with its content, makes a certain contribution to the formation of elements of a scientific worldview in students. This work is done through reading lessons in primary grades.

Popular scientific texts and articles in textbooks are the main expression of thinking in the student. When thinking about popular scholarly texts and articles, first look deeper into their meaning. It is necessary to look for this article. Let's take a look at Henri. The article is derived from the Arabic word, which means speech, small work. It is also a small scientific or journalistic work written for or printed in a collection, magazine, newspaper, etc. Journalism is derived from the Latin word "publicus", which means "social" and is a special type of literature. It differs from scientific and artistic creations according to the style of writing. Journalistic works have their own style, just as works related to science are created in a scientific style, and examples of artistic creations are created in an artistic style. Journalistic works, first of all, are distinguished by their social spirit, unique only to journalism. If the main subject of science is scientific theory, and that of literature is humanities, the main subject of journalism is socio-political life, actual in material life problems. The uniqueness of the subject of the image, the direction of representation of reality and in terms of its different style, journalism is an independent type of creative field [1, 27-6.]. In addition, journalistic works are unique in that they are created for the purpose of evaluating a certain socio-political, material reality. Addressing the student in them, active participation in social reality the spirit of the challenge leads. After all, journalistic works are about life, existing social conditions, historical period in the reader understanding serves to create imagination. Ensuring the physical and spiritual maturity of the young generation - their future thinker is one of the most urgent issues facing every society. Since the first days of the independence of our republic, great attention has been paid to this problem also proof of our opinion can be Our independent country. The first order was named "For a healthy generation", the establishment of the "Healthy Generation" fund, the "Year of a Healthy Generation", "The Year of Mothers and Children" and the main essence of the events of the growing young generation. not only to ensure their physical, but also spiritual perfection, to educate them in the spirit of the thousands-year-old values of our people, patriotic feelings consists of forming Children's literature, which is one of

the main means of ensuring the spiritual maturity of the young generation, is of incomparable importance, along with textbooks and training manuals, samples of fiction, and popular scientific articles. After all, this genre example, as an example of contemporary creativity in elementary school textbooks, first of all conveys to the student the events taking place in social life. The comprehensively interpreted reality of the land and the breath of the times, our historical past, our ancestors, and great personalities, acquires a social essence, arouses deep observation and thought in the student, and acts as a spiritual leader, is one of the factors that determine the development of society. In this sense, the main goal of teaching popular scientific articles is to give children certain knowledge about nature, people's work and social life, to teach children to work independently with a book and to get specific knowledge from it. Teaching articles on historical topics in connection with appropriate pictures helps people to understand how our ancestors fought for a happy life, to improve their lives, to protect the Motherland from the enemy; children learn that work is the basis of life, that people's lives develop and prosper thanks to work.

It can be concluded that the popular scientific article itself is primarily a text. However, it is an article as a genre. At the same time, 10-15-line texts on scientific and popular topics are given in the 1st grade reading book. It's better to call them texts than popular science articles. After all, in such texts, the article-specific observation, reasoning is not the leader. Basically, information is provided. 1st grade reading book «Amir Texts such as Temur», «Great Teacher», «King and Poet», "Great Astrologer", "Sultan of the Estate of Ghazal" provide only preliminary scientific information about great thinkers. We think that it is appropriate to use them in the form of a text rather than a popular scientific article. In the textbooks of the 3rd-4th grade, there are texts of a larger volume, which reflect on a topical social topic, or provide more scientific information about historical figures, our ancestors. Since they express the features of the scientific-popular article genre, it is appropriate to apply the concept exactly. Moreover, this application is correct according to the age characteristics of the 1st graders. At this point, it is appropriate to clarify the term.

Because methodologists use the concept in the form of "popular scientific work", "article", "text". Most of the texts in the 1-2 grade reading books do not meet the requirements of the genre of a work or an article. Their style of expression is also quite simple. More precisely, close to a more formal style. Accordingly, all socio-historical content aimed at "giving certain knowledge about nature, human labor and social life". 50-100-word pieces of scientific-popular we believe that it is better to study as a whole in the form of a text. In particular, most of the texts related to socio-historical, scientific or natural phenomena in the 1st grade textbook have a very concise and simple narrative style. Expressing them in the form of an article or piece is so journalistic and is not grounded in the literary phenomenon. Therefore, the professional and literary knowledge of primary school teachers plays an important role in explaining such texts to a small student. So, in the 1st grade reading book, the scientific information on the social topic, historical figures, thinkers' life is concise, from 4-5 verses to 10-15 lines in the form of popular scientific texts; In essence, it is reasonable to use the texts in the textbooks of the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th grades, which are saturated with opinions about social and life issues, historical figures, life events, and great thinkers, in the form of scientific and popular articles.

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